

Flavonoids from the flowers of *Acacia farnesiana* Willd.

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Acacia farnesiana Willd. (Family : Leguminosie) is regarded as native of tropical America and is cosmopolitan in tropics. It has now spread itself throughout the greater part of India. The fragrant yellow globose flowers of the plant are a source of much valued cassie perfume.¹ No mention, so far, appears to have been made of the presence of flavonoids. The isolation of a crystalline flavonoid compound from the flowers of the species and its structure determination are now reported.

The ethanol extract on purification by suitable solvent fractionation followed by chromatography on polyamide column yielded a crystalline glycoside m.p. 216–19° (methanol). The homogeneity of the product was established by paper chromatography in a number of solvent systems and also by TLC.

The glycoside gave positive cyanidin test² both in acid as well as in alkaline media. Wilson boric acid test³ confirmed it to be a flavonol-3-glycoside. On acid hydrolysis, it gave an aglycone m.p. 302–304° and sugars.

The aglycone has been characterised as 3'-methoxy-3',5,7,4'-tetrahydroxy flavonol (isorhamnetin) by its melting and mixed melting points, R_f value and co-chromatography and also by spectral studies⁴ : U.V. absorption λ_{max}^{EtOH} 265 m μ , 375 m μ ; I.R. absorption : ν_{max}^{Nujol} 1655 and 3160 cm⁻¹; and N.M.R. (trimethyl silylated aglycone) : doublet 6.10 at C₆; doublet 6.4 at C₈; doublet 7.6 at C₂-; doublet 6.80 at C₅-; quartet 7.54 at C₆-; singlet 3.81 at C₃- . The aglycone gave an acetate, m.p. 202–204° (alcohol).

The hydrolysate on chromatographic examination showed the presence of glucose and rhamnose as the carbohydrate moiety. The methylation of the glycoside followed by hydrolysis gave 3-, 4-, 5- trimethoxy-quercetin m.p. 292°⁵ locating the sugars at C-3 and C-7. The structure of the glycoside and the location of the rhamnoside moiety at C-7 and that of glucoside moiety at C-3 has been fully established by N.M.R. studies of trimethyl silyl derivative of the glycoside.

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The quantitative estimation of the sugars by Somogyi's copper micro method⁶ showed the presence of two moles of sugars per mole of aglycone. The glycoside m.p. 216-19° is therefore characterised as isorhamnetin-3,7-glucorhamnoside. The details of the work will be reported elsewhere.

The authors are grateful to Prof. Tom J. Mabry, University of Texas, (U.S.A.), for running N.M.R.

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Received July 1, 1969.

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